

Effect of Substance Induction via Intraperitoneal Injection on Cardiac Histopathological Changes and Blood Glucose Levels in Test Animals

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Organ histopathological research is one of the important approaches in understanding the toxic and therapeutic effects of various substances on the body. In this context, the heart and blood are very vital organs and are sensitive to physiological changes induced by foreign substances (Buana, 2022). In addition, blood glucose level is a key parameter in determining the metabolic status and homeostasis of the body, which can be affected by various pharmacological and toxic agents (Santoso, 2021). The method of substance induction via intraperitoneal injection is one of the techniques often used in pre-clinical research with test animals. The intraperitoneal procedure involves a ½ or ¼ inch needle inserted into the midline of the ventral abdomen (Swart et al. 2008). This method allows for a more rapid and even distribution of the substance in the test animal's body, as well as minimising variations caused by other routes of administration (Shayne, 2014). However, the use of this method in studies of cardiac histopathology and blood glucose levels is still limited, thus providing opportunities for further exploration in this context. Histological analysis can be a very important parameter in determining changes in cell structure that occur in internal organs such as the heart. Microscopic observations with histology of certain organs are carried out to determine the relationship between the symptoms that occur with the structure of organs that experience exposure to test compounds (Adha, 2023). Observations are made on heart tissue preparations stained with HE stain, so that microscopic observations will show blue cell nuclei and red cytoplasm (Larasati et al., 2020). According to Bhara (2009), necrosis has levels including dead cell nuclei that will shrink, compact, irregular boundaries, and basophilic coloured with hematoxylin-eosin (HE) dye, such core conditions are called pycnotic. Furthermore, the cell nucleus can disintegrate and leave fragments of chromatin scattered in the cell, this process is called karyorrhexis. Hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) staining is one of the most frequently used stains in the field of histology to view the cells and structure of a tissue. Hematoxylin is a basic dye used to colour acidic structures with a purplish blue colour, usually used to colour the nucleus. Meanwhile, eosin is an acidic dye commonly used to colour basic structures red or pink which is generally used to dye cell cytoplasm (Wulan, 2020).

Metabolic disorders have the potential to increase other serious health problems including cardiovascular disease, liver steatosis, chronic kidney disease, tumours, and cancer. It is well documented that a high-sugar diet is closely linked to the development of diabetes and obesity (Santoso, 2019). Smoking is a major factor causing vascular disease (heart, brain and peripheral). Cigarettes contain nicotine, tar, and carbon monoxide (CO) that destabilise oxidants and antioxidants in the body. Putra (2018) proved that exposure to cigarette smoke every morning consecutively for 14 days caused inflammation in the heart of rats due to oxidative stress

(Farsalinos, 2014). Antioxidants are needed to stop the negative effects that free radicals can cause. Antioxidants are starting to be used more frequently as people become more aware of their ability to prevent degenerative diseases including cancer, heart disease, arteriosclerosis, and aging-related symptoms. Antioxidants are chemical substances that can give free radicals one or more electrons, thus preventing them from doing damage (Kamaruddin, 2023).

There is a trend to reduce oxidative stress in the body by consuming antioxidants from herbal plants. One of them is polyphenols that can capture free radicals 100 times more effectively than vitamin C and 25 times more effectively than vitamin E (Qasim, 2017). DM is characterised by hyperglycaemia. Sustained hyperglycaemia causes oxidative stress, leading to damage to nerves, blood vessels in different tissues and serious complications (Rina and Santoso, 2022). Swastini et al. (2018) conducted a study on the reduction of blood glucose levels by giving palm sugar to male Wistar rats induced by alloxan, resulting in data that the negative test group experienced a significant increase. Another study was conducted by Muntafiah et al. (2019) in the DM control group (group II) using alloxan monohydrate 120mg/kg BW intraperitoneally confirmed to experience hyperglycaemia conditions on day 5 after injection after previously being fed for 12 hours. By understanding the mechanism and effects of substances induced through this route, it is expected to make an important contribution to the field of toxicology and pharmacology, and fill the existing research gap.

These studies aim to evaluate the effect of substance induction via intraperitoneal injection on cardiac histopathological changes and blood glucose levels in test animals. Understanding the mechanisms and effects of substances induced via this route is expected to make important contributions to the fields of toxicology and pharmacology (Almahdy, 2023) and fill existing research gaps. In this study, several important factors will be considered, including the type of substance induced, the dose used, and the duration of exposure (Maksum and Nurfadillah, 2020.). In addition, histopathological analysis will be conducted to identify structural changes in tissues such as the liver kidney and heart (Worotikan, 2018), while blood glucose levels will be measured to assess the metabolic effects of the substance. The results of this study are expected to provide new insights into the impact of intraperitoneal injection on cardiovascular health and glucose metabolism, as well as assist in the development of more effective and safe treatment strategies.

This study aims to evaluate the effect of substance induction via intraperitoneal injection on cardiac histopathological changes and blood glucose levels in test animals. The study is expected to make important contributions to the fields of toxicology and pharmacology and fill existing research gaps. This study is important because it fills a knowledge gap on how substance induction via intraperitoneal injection affects cardiovascular health and glucose metabolism, which has not previously been widely studied. An in-depth understanding of these effects will not only enrich the scientific literature but also potentially lead to the development of more effective and safe treatment strategies. Therefore, this study has a high relevance and urgency in a scientific and medical context.

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